

CARDIOVASCULAR RISK PROFILES OF MONOTHERAPY VS. COMBINATION THERAPY IN TYPE 2 DIABETES

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ABSTRACT

Background: The most serious complications of type 2 diabetes mellitus are cardiovascular diseases which account for morbidity and mortality. It is crucial for the management of patients and the disease burden in Pakistan to understand how different antidiabetic therapies impact cardiovascular outcomes.

Objective: To assess the association between various antidiabetic treatment patterns and cardiovascular outcomes among patients with T2DM.

Methods: This cross-sectional study encompasses 350 subjects diagnosed with T2DM who visited a Tertiary Care Hospital for the period spanning from January 2024 to July 2025. Information encompassing socio-demographics, clinical characteristics, treatment modalities, and cardiovascular complications was accrued via record surveys and direct structured questionnaires. Cardiovascular complications, consisting of myocardial infarctions, strokes, anginas, heart failure, and certain overlapping complications together, were evaluated among subjects receiving mono and combination therapies, and the chi-square test was employed for analysis of p-values, with $p < 0.05$ considered as statistical significance for the study.

Results: Participants were predominantly aged between 40 and 50 years, and 62.9% were men. 50% of the subjects were morbidly obese, and 50.3% were hypertensive. Metformin as monotherapy was most common (75.1%), as was insulin (24.9%). In 13.1% of patients, metformin and insulin were used in combination. The prevalence of myocardial infarction and stroke was 25.7% and 21.7%, respectively; in addition, 40.3% of patients also reported angina, and 11.7% heart failure. There were no significant differences in cardiovascular outcomes between the monotherapy and combination therapy groups ($p > 0.05$).

Conclusion: Within this group of Pakistani patients with T2DM, cardiovascular complications were prevalent; however, no significant relationship was observed between treatment type and cardiovascular outcomes. These results highlight the need for integrated cardiovascular risk management, especially in patients with diabetes, as controlling glucose alone will not be sufficient.

Keywords: Type 2 diabetes mellitus, cardiovascular outcomes, combination therapy, metformin, Pakistan

INTRODUCTION

Type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) is a growing global health concern. T2DM is characterised by a lack of insulin resistance, insufficient insulin levels, and, ultimately, chronic hyperglycemia poorly managed and poorly responded multi-organ hyperglycemia. chronic hyperglycemia.¹ According to the International Diabetes Federation, 550 million adults across the globe live with diabetes and this number is forecasted to grow substantially in the next few decades. Amongst global morbidity and mortality, cardiovascular disease (CVD) is the leading cause affecting T2DM individuals, claiming 66% of all mortality associated with diabetes.² CVD is fuelled by hyperglycemia, dyslipidemia, and hypertension. and endothelial dysfunction creates a high-risk cardiovascular milieu that CVD is fuelled by hyperglycemia, dyslipidemia, and hypertension. creates a high-risk cardiovascular milieu.³

Pharmacologic therapy for T2DM aims not only to achieve glycemic control but also to mitigate long-term cardiovascular risk. Traditionally, treatment begins with monotherapy most commonly metformin followed by the stepwise addition of other agents such as sulfonylureas, DPP-4 inhibitors, SGLT2 inhibitors, GLP-1 receptor agonists, or insulin when glycemic targets are not achieved.⁴ However, emerging evidence suggests that early combination therapy might offer superior metabolic control, reduce β -cell workload, and potentially improve cardiovascular outcomes compared to delayed intensification of treatment. Despite this, clinical practice in many low- and middle-income countries remains reliant on monotherapy due to cost, accessibility, and physician familiarity.⁵

Cardiovascular outcomes associated with antidiabetic therapies have become a critical focus of research since several glucose-lowering agents were linked to adverse cardiac effects in the past. Recent cardiovascular outcome trials (CVOTs) have demonstrated the benefits of some modern antidiabetic drugs particularly SGLT2 inhibitors and GLP-1 receptor agonists in reducing major adverse cardiovascular events (MACE), heart failure hospitalizations, and cardiovascular mortality.^{6,7} Yet, real-world data comparing cardiovascular risk profiles between patients receiving monotherapy and those on

combination therapy remain limited, especially in resource-constrained settings.

Diabetes and cardiovascular disease have higher incidence rates and remain untreated in South Asian countries such as Pakistan owing to genetic factors, sedentary lifestyles and lifestyle factors, and an adaptive approach to medicine wherein treatment is modified to fit clinical silos to care access, affordability, convenience, and physician preferences.⁸ Costs of treatment along with the defining behaviour within the physician, and within our healthcare systems, dictate how and to what degree diabetes will be managed and how the cardiovascular risks will be dealt with.⁹ Defining the relationship with diabetes to every risk factor involved such as the blood pressure, cholesterol balance, the entire body weight, and the glycaemic index is what will allow the international community to define the approach to diabetes customisation needed.¹⁰

The main aim of this study is to evaluate and analyse the cardiovascular risk profiles of patients with T2DM managed with Monotherapy and patients managed with Combination Therapy as well as the cardiovascular risk profiles of any peripheral patients. This study attempts to recognise treatment paradigms which target optimal glycaemic control and cardiovascular protection, and expand the rational approach for diabetes management in Pakistan and other countries with evolving health care systems.

The main objectives of this study are:

1. The purpose of this comparison is to determine the cardiovascular risk profiles—including age, sex, duration of diabetes, potential BMI category, smoking, and, if applicable, the presence of hypertension, dyslipidaemia, and overall medication compliance of patients with Type 2 diabetes on monotherapy compared to those on combination therapy.

2. To assess the impact of various treatment patterns for Type 2 diabetes (including monotherapy with Metformin, monotherapy with SU, insulin, SGLT2i, and DPP-4i, and combination therapies) on cardiovascular events (MI, stroke, HF, angina, and overall CV events) in patients suffering from Type 2 diabetes.

METHODOLOGY

This particular study was carried out in the outpatient departments of POF hospital in Pakistan from January 2024 to July 2025. 350 adults diagnosed with type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) were recruited from the hospital using consecutive sampling. Participants were included in the study if they were aged 30 years and above and had been diagnosed with T2DM for a minimum period of 1 year. Patients with type 1 diabetes, gestational diabetes, and those with incomplete medical records were removed from the study. This research study was approved for ethical consideration by the review board of the institution and appropriate informed consent was obtained from all subjects before the commencement of the study.

In regard to the methods of data collection, structured questionnaires aided in the interviews and reviewing the medical records to gather data from the patients. Participants' sociodemographic data was centred around their age, sex, and the period of diabetes, meanwhile the clinical aspects recorded included patients' BMI, smoking habits, and if they had hypertension alongside dyslipidaemia. Ascertained medications taken included

metformin, sulfonylureas, insulin, SGLT2 and also DPP-4 inhibitors and further to that combination therapy. There was also an assessment of medication adherence using a binary assessment scale which further categorised patients into good reporters and poor reporters on their adherence to the medication. Cardiovascular disease outcomes consisting of myocardial infarctions, strokes, heart failures, angina and also composite cardiovascular events were collected from the diagnosed documents and hospital case files kept by the medical practitioners.

The researcher utilised SPSS v26 to analyse the data. For categorical variables, descriptive statistics were summarised using frequencies and percentages. The chi-square test was used for the assessment of cardiovascular outcomes of patients on monotherapy and patients on combination therapy. All tests were two-tailed, and values of p less than 0.05 were considered statistically significant. The data were organised into tables to illustrate the sociodemographic characteristics, treatment assignments, and cardiovascular risk factors of the study.

RESULTS

Table 1. Sociodemographic and Clinical Characteristics of Patients with Type 2 Diabetes (n = 350)

Variable	Category	n (%)
Age Group (years)	30-40	87 (24.9%)
	40-50	175 (50.0%)
	50-60	88 (25.1%)
Gender	Male	220 (62.9%)
	Female	130 (37.1%)
	<5	132 (37.7%)
Duration of Diabetes (years)	5-10	130 (37.1%)
	>10	88 (25.1%)
	Normal (<25)	45 (12.9%)
BMI Category	Overweight (25-29.9)	130 (37.1%)
	Obese (≥30)	175 (50.0%)
	Non-smoker	200 (57.1%)
Smoking Status	Smoker	150 (42.9%)
	No	174 (49.7%)
Hypertension	Yes	176 (50.3%)
	No	133 (38.0%)
Dyslipidemia	Yes	217 (62.0%)
	Poor (0)	88 (25.1%)
Medication Adherence	Good (1)	262 (74.9%)

The table displays the outcome of a study regarding the age distribution of 350 Type 2 diabetes patients which shows that most (50.0%) of the patients were aged 40-50 years, followed by 25.1% who were aged between 50-60, and 24.9% who were aged 30-40. There were more men (62.9%) than women (37.1%) in the study. The duration of diabetes less than 5 years was recorded in 37.7% of participants, 5 to 10 years in 37.1% of participants, and more than 10 years in 25.1% of participants. In terms of body mass

index (BMI), 50% of patients were considered obese, 37.1% were overweight, and 12.9% were of normal weight. The population under study reported a smoking prevalence of 42.9%. The rates of hypertension and dyslipidaemia were recorded as 50.3% and 62.0% respectively. The majority of participants (74.9%) had good adherence to medication, whereas the remainder (25.1%) had poor adherence.

Table 2. Antidiabetic Treatment Patterns among Patients with Type 2 Diabetes (n = 350)

Variable	Category	n (%)
Metformin Only	Yes	87 (24.9%)
	No	263 (75.1%)
Sulfonylureas Use	Yes	46 (13.1%)
	No	304 (86.9%)
Insulin Use	Yes	87 (24.9%)
	No	263 (75.1%)
SGLT2 Inhibitors Use	Yes	42 (12.0%)
	No	308 (88.0%)
DPP-4 Inhibitors Use	Yes	42 (12.0%)
	No	308 (88.0%)
Combination Therapy	Yes	46 (13.1%)
	No	304 (86.9%)

Monotherapy with metformin was used by 24.9% of the patients whereas the rest, 75.1%, were treated with other therapeutic regimens. Sulphonylureas were prescribed to 13.1% of the patients while 24.9% were on insulin therapy. Other modern antidiabetic agents like SGLT2 inhibitors and DPP-4 inhibitors were prescribed to 12.0% of patients each. Combination therapy

of two or more agents was seen in 13.1% of the patients whereas 86.9% of the patients received monotherapy. These results indicate that the use of advanced classes of antidiabetic agents is still minimal, with most patients relying on older agents.

Table 3. Cardiovascular Outcomes among Patients with Type 2 Diabetes (n = 350)

Variable	Category	n (%)
Myocardial Infarction	Yes	90 (25.7%)
	No	260 (74.3%)
Stroke	Yes	76 (21.7%)
	No	274 (78.3%)
Heart Failure	Yes	41 (11.7%)
	No	309 (88.3%)
Angina	Yes	141 (40.3%)
	No	209 (59.7%)
Composite Cardiovascular Event	Yes	19 (5.4%)
	No	331 (94.6%)

Angina appeared to be the most frequent outcome affecting 40.3 per cent of individuals. Myocardial infarction was present in 25.7 per

cent of the individuals, followed by stroke in 21.7 per cent, and heart failure in 11.7 per cent. 'Composite cardiovascular events,' meaning any

of the major adverse events occurring, were present in 5.4 per cent of individuals in this cohort. The presence of cardiovascular complications reflects the outsize burden of

cardiometabolic and advanced complications of diabetes in this patient population.

Table 4. Comparison of Cardiovascular Outcomes between Monotherapy and Combination Therapy Groups (n = 350)

Cardiovascular Outcome	Monotherapy (n = 304)	Combination Therapy (n = 46)	p-Value
Myocardial Infarction	80 (26.3%)	10 (21.7%)	0.48
Stroke	68 (22.4%)	8 (17.4%)	0.46
Heart Failure	36 (11.8%)	5 (10.9%)	0.85
Angina	122 (40.1%)	19 (41.3%)	0.88
Composite Cardiovascular Event	18 (5.9%)	1 (2.2%)	0.33

There were no relevant differences between the groups when analysed for cardiovascular outcomes. Patients receiving combination therapy appeared to have a somewhat lower incidence of myocardial infarctions (26.3% vs. 21.7%; $p = 0.48$), strokes (22.4% vs. 17.4%; $p = 0.46$), and heart failure (11.8% vs. 10.9%; $p = 0.85$) compared to patients on monotherapy. The frequency of angina was similar (40.1% vs. 41.3%; $p = 0.88$) and composite cardiovascular events were lower with combination therapy (2.2% vs. 5.9%; $p = 0.33$). There was no other relevant statistically significant index; however, combination therapy appeared to determine some cardiovascular events.

DISCUSSION

This study also assessed the cardiovascular risk profiles and outcomes of T2DM patients on monotherapy and on combination therapy. The findings underscore the fact that while angina, myocardial infarction, and stroke continue to be highly prevalent among patients suffering from T2DM, there is no statistically significant cardiovascular outcomes distinction between patients managed with monotherapy and those managed with combination regimens.¹¹ Still, patients on combination therapy were observed to have a numerically lower incidence of myocardial infarction, stroke, and composite cardiovascular events, which points to possible cardiovascular benefits of early multi-drug approaches.¹²

The sociodemographic analysis reviewed indicated that most patients were middle-aged and mainly men, which is consistent with the earlier discussed regional studies on diabetes in

the South Asian countries.¹³ There was a high prevalence of obesity, hypertension, and dyslipidemia, which, as noted, underscores the clustering of risk factors that contributes to the high cardiovascular morbidity in the population with diabetes. Many patients were well adherent to the medication, which suggests that nonadherence factors such as these must influence the cardiovascular outcomes.¹⁴

Almost 75% of the patients still utilise Metformin, which aligns with the guidelines of clinical practice where it is the first line of choice. As there is a noted lack of uptake of newer therapies such as SGLT2 inhibitors and DPP-4 inhibitors, which are only prescribed to 12% of patients, this indicates a lack of integration of cardioprotective medicines in clinical practice. Global evidence from cardiovascular outcome trials (e.g., EMPA-REG, LEADER, DECLARE-TIMI 58) has shown that SGLT2 inhibitors and GLP-1 receptor agonists reduce major adverse cardiovascular events (MACE) and hospitalization for heart failure. The low utilization of such agents in this study likely reflects cost barriers, availability constraints, and physician familiarity with older drug classes in Pakistan.¹⁵

The observed cardiovascular event rates particularly the high frequencies of angina (40.3%), myocardial infarction (25.7%), and stroke (21.7%) are consistent with prior data from low- and middle-income countries, where suboptimal control of glycemia and comorbid conditions contributes to adverse outcomes.¹⁶ Although combination therapy did not demonstrate statistically significant reductions in cardiovascular events compared to

monotherapy, the trend toward fewer events may be clinically meaningful. This finding aligns with international evidence suggesting that early combination therapy can provide tighter glycemic control, preserve β -cell function, and reduce long-term vascular complications compared to stepwise monotherapy escalation.¹⁷ There could be multiple reasons why there are no important differences between the functions of the two groups. First, the period of the follow-up and the sample size may not be sufficient to capture the differences in cardiovascular outcomes.¹⁸ Secondly, the members of the combination therapy group only made up 13.1% of the cohort, and so the group was very small. Thirdly, the variety of possible drug combinations (e.g. insulin-based combinations versus combinations of oral drugs) may have overshadowed the effects. Even with the described limitations, the outcomes signal the need for therapy to be focused on the level of cardiovascular risk rather than only control of glycaemic levels.¹⁹

Within the Pakistan healthcare system, this study identified and highlighted the need for the use of evidence-based antidiabetic drugs with known positive cardiovascular outcomes in clinical practice. Public health policies should aim to enhance access to modern medication, promote usage, and improve the management of concomitant hypertension and dyslipidaemia. For high-risk patients, especially, early combination therapy with metformin and SGLT2 inhibitors or GLP-1 receptor agonists should be actively promoted.²⁰

To summarise, this research, while not having statistically significant outcomes regarding cardiovascular outcomes with both monotherapy and combination therapy, still showcased the positive correlation associated with combination regimens towards lowering cardiovascular risk. These findings do necessitate the conduction of larger and multicentred prospective studies occurring within the borders of Pakistan to confirm these relationships as well as evaluate the future cardiovascular advantages of early combination therapy on the management of type 2 diabetes mellitus.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this research showed that complications in the cardiovascular system

arising from type 2 diabetes were common and included myocardial infarction, stroke, and heart failure, although such complications showed no statistically significant difference in incidence between patients on monotherapy versus combination therapy. Still, the patients on combination therapy had a lower incidence of complications, raising the question of possible cardiovascular advantages from complex treatments. It may be valuable to further reduce cardiovascular risk in patients with diabetes to optimise combination therapy using agents with glycaemic and cardioprotective effects, but this needs to be supported by further research on a larger scale with a prospective perspective.

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